

Protecting The Rights, Freedoms And Principles That Guarantee Them In The Jordanian Constitution And Its Amendments

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Human Rights, Fundamental Freedoms, Supremacy Of The Constitution, Democratic System, Legal State, Rule Of Law, Separation Of Powers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4813097</p>	<p><i>Respecting the rights and freedoms of citizens is an indicator of the democratic system of government. It illustrates the extent of the state's concern for the dignity of its citizens, and its keenness to safeguard their rights and freedoms from any aggression against it by the public authorities. This leads to enhancing the citizen's belonging to his homeland and unleashing his energies to achieve the desired progress. The constitutional protection of rights and freedoms is one of the most effective means of protection, due to the importance the constitution enjoys in the legal state. All ruling authorities must respect its provisions as they derive their legitimacy and competencies from it. Based on the democratic approach adopted by Jordan, the Jordanian constitutional legislator has been keen to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens by explicitly stipulating in the Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments on a number of rights and freedoms enjoyed by citizens, which the public authorities must respect, and not violate or diminish them. Including, and even enabling citizens to enjoy and practice them. Which represents a direct protection of those rights and freedoms, as he was keen to adopt a number of constitutional principles on which the legal state is based and adopted by democratic systems, such as the principle of the nation's sovereignty and the separation of powers, and the supremacy of the constitution, which creates, through their interaction and integration, a suitable environment for protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens and ensuring their exercise And not to assault her.</i></p> <p><i>This research comes to shed light on constitutionally protected rights and freedoms in accordance with the provisions of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments, and the extent of the effectiveness of the constitutional principles guaranteeing them in protecting them and ensuring their practice.</i></p>

Introduction

The constitution is the first guarantee for the realization of the legal state, as it is the one that creates the legal system in the state and comes at the top of the legal hierarchy in it, and therefore it is not permissible for any law to contradict its provisions. The constitution defines the jurisdiction of each of the public authorities that it creates. Therefore, all public authorities are subject to the constitution that created them, defined their powers, and indicated how they were formed (1).

The constitution derives His Highness from the fact that it "establishes the notion of law prevalent in the state and defines the philosophy and ideology upon which the applicable legal system is based, whether in political, social or economic terms. It defines the public authorities in the state (legislative, executive and judicial) and delineates their functions, and sets limits and controlling restrictions Because of its activities, it determines public freedoms and rights, and obliges those authorities to abide by the rules and principles of the constitution and adhere to its limits and restrictions, if they violate them or exceed them, their work will be punished by the defect of violating the constitution (2).

And based on the supreme position that the constitution occupies in the modern state, most countries of the world that adopt the democratic approach seek to include in their constitutions a number of freedoms and rights that they guarantee to their citizens (3).

Since Jordan is one of the leading democratic countries in the Arab region, the Jordanian constitutional legislator has been keen since the establishment of this state to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, and this was evident in the Basic Law of the Emirate of Transjordan in 1928. And in the Constitution of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan of 1946, through texts clearly constitutional and all public authorities in the state must respect it and ensure its implementation and work with its content, which constitutes a direct constitutional protection of these freedoms and rights. It also stipulated a number of constitutional principles that guarantee citizens' enjoyment of these freedoms and rights, which constitutes indirect constitutional protection for them.

In this research, the researcher will try to shed light on what freedoms and rights are and their types, as mentioned in the texts of the Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments, and then clarifies the constitutional principles that guarantee and protect those rights and freedoms.

Research problem: Although the term citizens' rights and freedoms is a common term that is frequently used by most scholars and researchers in the field of constitutional law, political systems, human rights and political science, the expansion of this concept has led to some confusion and ambiguity in its understanding. Also, the idea of the constitutional protection of these rights and freedoms is not limited to the inclusion of constitutional texts that clarify these freedoms and rights, which represents a direct protection for them - and this protection is often represented by clarity and simplicity - rather it is necessary to create constitutional guarantees that are not directly related to the idea of rights and freedoms, but they do. To create an appropriate climate for these rights and freedoms to flourish, the citizens' enjoyment and protection of them, and without the constitutional guarantees that constitute the indirect protection of rights and freedoms, citizens will not enjoy them in a realistic way. These rights and freedoms will not be protected from any aggression or derogation.

Importance of the research: This research sheds light on the issue of the rights and freedoms of citizens, how to protect them and guarantees for their exercise, and the constitutional principles adopted by the Jordanian constitution and which provide the appropriate climate for the maintenance of these rights and freedoms, and it is one of the important topics because the citizen's enjoyment of his rights and freedoms is a factor of strength for the state, and guarantees protection. The dignity of the citizen and enhances his belonging to his homeland.

The research objectives:

To clarify what rights and freedoms are and their types and to study the constitutional principles guaranteeing them those were stipulated by the Jordanian constitutional legislator to protect them in the 1952 constitution and its amendments. These guarantees are an indirect protection for rights and freedoms, despite the fact that they are related to other constitutional issues such as the system of government, the judiciary, etc.

Research methodology: The researcher will follow the analytical approach by analyzing the texts of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments related to rights and freedoms. And the constitutional texts related to the constitutional principles guaranteeing it, which provide indirect constitutional protection for these rights and freedoms. They are guarantees that must be in place to create a suitable environment for citizens to enjoy and exercise them, and not to violate them or diminish them and protect them.

Research questions:

1. What is the concept of rights and freedoms?
2. How are rights and freedoms classified?
3. What types of rights and freedoms are constitutionally protected in the Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments?
4. What are the constitutional principles that guarantee rights and freedoms in the Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments?
5. To what extent is the indirect constitutional protection of the rights and freedoms provided by the constitutional principles that guarantee them in the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments to ensure that citizens enjoy them and defend them, and not to violate or diminish them?

Concept of rights and freedoms:

When we talk about the concept of rights in the field of the constitutional protection of rights and freedoms, we mean by that human rights, which Karl Vasak defined as: "Those rights that should be recognized for a person simply because he is a human being, and they differ from positive rights in that the latter depend on the condition of legal protection for them.

As for freedom, Article 4 of the Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the French Citizen of 1789, issued after the French Revolution, defined it as: "The ability to perform every action that does not harm others," and the aforementioned article adds ... "The exercise of natural freedoms cannot be subjected to restrictions except in order to empower members. The community of others can enjoy their rights and these restrictions may only be imposed by law" (4).

Therefore, the Encyclopedia of Politics has defined freedom as: "a general political, economic, philosophical and moral concept, with multiple and complex connotations, each of which needs a certain level of definition and definition. There is freedom of religion, freedom of expression, freedom of information, freedom of association and assembly, and freedom of trade." (5).

It seems that there is an overlap and intermingling between the concept of rights and freedoms. Therefore, the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen described human rights as freedoms that allow everyone to live his private life in the manner he deems appropriate. Freedom is a right to be established, and the right is freedom to practice, that is, when a right is recognized. A person has the freedom to use or exercise this right. Consequently, the difference between freedom and truth is nothing but a verbal difference, and it does not go beyond it to the difference in meaning (6).

The French jurist Rivero defined constitutionally protected rights and freedoms as: "a set of recognized rights and freedoms that were considered fundamental to a certain civilized level" (7).

Finally, we point out that constitutionally protected rights and freedoms are expressed in different forms, including public rights and freedoms, fundamental rights and freedoms, and some believe: "There is a disagreement between the two terms, as public rights and freedoms are guaranteed by the constitution and the law together. As for basic rights and freedoms, they are guaranteed by the constitution alone. This is because fundamental rights and freedoms are closely related to the rules that are superior to ordinary legislation and amount to constitutional norms" (8).

The researcher will study the rights and freedoms that are protected by the Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments, without distinguishing between them on the basis that they are basic or general, because the title of the research is the protection of rights and freedoms and the principles that guarantee them. Therefore, when we study the constitutional protection of rights and freedoms in the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments, we will deal with the constitutional texts that dealt with each right or freedom separately without discrimination.

Classification of rights and freedoms:

There are several classifications of rights and freedoms, but we will suffice to mention some of them:

1 - Aspect of jurisprudence believes that rights and freedoms are classified into:

A- Rights and freedoms related to the person of the human being: through which the person asserts his existence and independence. These include the right to security, freedom of private life, freedom of thought, the right to property, the right to assembly, the right to practice religious rites, and freedom of movement (9).

B - Social and economic rights and freedoms: These are the rights that guarantee a certain standard of living in terms of material and moral, and thus place on the state an obligation to intervene by making a positive effort to secure their enjoyment, the right to work, the right to education, the right to health and the right to join trade unions (10).

2- As for the French jurist Digi, he divided freedoms into two parts:

A- Negative freedoms: They impose a negative obligation on the authority that is merely abstaining from infringing upon them, as they are restrictions on the state's power.

B - Positive freedoms: that imposes on the authority a positive obligation that requires the state to intervene to enable individuals to enjoy these freedoms (11).

3- The French jurist Eastman also divided rights and freedoms into two parts:

A- Civil equality: includes equality before the law and equality before taxes.

B- Individual freedoms: are divided into:

-Freedoms with a material content

-Freedoms with a moral content (12).

4- There are other classifications, including the classification of freedoms based on the reality of historical development (13).

The researcher believes that the last classification is the classification followed by most researchers in the field of human rights, as most of the literature follows this classification.

Rights and freedoms protected in the Jordanian constitution and its amendments

Rights and freedoms have enjoyed the attention of the Jordanian constitutional legislator since the birth of the Emirate of Transjordan. The Basic Law of Transjordan of 1928 stipulated in the first chapter of Article 4 through Article 14 thereof, a number of rights and freedoms enjoyed by citizens under the title (the rights of the people). In reference to his desire to establish a constitutional state concerned with the rights and freedoms of the people, on the basis that the people are the source of authority (14), and among the rights and freedoms that enjoy constitutional protection under the Basic Law of 1928, equality before the law, personal freedom, the inviolability of housing, and the right to litigate The right to property, freedom of work, freedom of belief and freedom of opinion (15).

When the Constitution of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan was issued in 1946, it stipulated in its first chapter the same rights of the people as contained in the Basic Law of 1928 (16).

However, when the Constitution of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan issued in the current 1952 was issued, the Jordanian constitutional legislator devoted a separate chapter to rights and freedoms (17), which is the second chapter under the title (Rights and duties of Jordanians). The aforementioned constitution provided for the regulation of rights and freedoms in a comprehensive, clear and precise manner (18), and this regulation was in line with international charters and agreements and the latest global trends (19). The constitutional protection of rights and freedoms has been strengthened according to the amendments that were made on 10/1/2011 (20), as the text on these rights and freedoms includes direct constitutional protection for them, given that the constitution is the supreme law in the state, which requires all individuals and public authorities in the state Respecting the provisions of these texts, which means ensuring that citizens enjoy these freedoms, because failure to respect these constitutional texts is a violation of the principle of legality, and therefore it is incumbent upon the legislative authority when developing a specific law to take into account these rights and freedoms and not diminish them, and if it violates that, the legislation Those issued by it will be described as unconstitutional,

which must be abolished by the judiciary that has been entrusted by the constitution with the function of monitoring the constitutionality of laws. In addition, the executive authority must also respect these rights and freedoms. If the administration violates the constitutional provisions and encroaches on the rights and freedoms of individuals, its behavior will be stigmatized as null and be subject to revocation and compensation according to a judgment issued by the judiciary, if its behavior is legal, and is subject to compensation. If it is a material behavior, the researchers will try to shed light on the constitutional texts that include direct protection of the rights and freedoms contained in the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments, without elaborating on their explanation, through the following:

First - Equality before the law:

The first paragraph of Article 6 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states the following: 1 - Jordanians are equal before the law in terms of rights and duties, even if they differ in race, language, or religion.

It provides for equality in general and equality before the law in Article (1), Article (2) and Article (7) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, and so have Article (3), Article (14), and Article (26) of the International Covenant (Civil Rights and Politics of 1966). Islamic law has guaranteed equality among people, equality in rights and duties, and equality before the law, because without achieving human equality, human dignity will not be safeguarded, and his humanity will be violated, and if people are not equal before the law, the law will become ineffective and just ink on paper.

The Jordanian constitutional legislator's affirmation of the principle of equality came from the fact that equality is the main key to achieving a sound democracy, because the state in which there is no equality is rife with injustice and the spirit of discrimination and hatred prevails, which exposes the social fabric to fragmentation and leads to the occurrence of turmoil and chaos that engulfs an entity. The state warns of its demise (21).

Second - Personal Freedom:

Article 7 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952, amended on 1/10/2011, states the following: 1 - Personal freedom is safeguarded. 2 - Any violation of public rights and freedoms or the inviolability of the private life of Jordanians is a crime punishable by law.

Personal freedom is defined broadly as: "A center that the individual enjoys whereby the authority can be prevented from exposure to some aspects of his basic or original activities that his daily life depends on securing, and on this it is a necessity that the individual cannot imagine dispensing with on the one hand, and on the other hand it is a center for the individual in the face of authority "(22).

And confirmation of the Jordanian Constitutional Law of 1952 to protect personal freedom, Article 8 of the constitution amended in 2011 stipulated the following: 1 - It is not permissible for anyone to be arrested, arrested, imprisoned or restricted except in accordance with the provisions of the law 2- Whoever is arrested He must be treated in a manner that preserves the dignity of the human being, and it is not permissible to torture him in any way or to harm him physically or morally, nor may he be detained in places other than those permitted by the laws and every statement made by any person under the burden of torture or harm Or an insignificant threat. "

This article corresponds to Articles (3), (5), (9) and (13) of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and Articles (7), (9), and (12) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of the year 1948. 1966. This article guarantees that public authorities will not violate the personal freedom of citizens, imprison them, restrict their freedom, or torture them, because this assault is inconsistent with human dignity and rights. This article guarantees that the Jordanian citizen remains dear and dignified in his country, and is not subjected to any practice It detracts from its dignity or humanity, because the pride of the country flourishes with the pride of its citizens.

Third - Freedom of Residence and Movement:

Article 9 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952, amended in 2011, states: "1- A Jordanian may not be deported from the Kingdom's homes 2- It is not permissible for a Jordanian to reside in a place or be prevented from moving, nor is he obliged to reside in a specific place except in Conditions set forth in the law. "

Article 13 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 affirmed the freedom of residence and movement, and stipulated this freedom in Article 12 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966. This freedom is one of the natural rights and freedoms that a person should enjoy and not the state limits it except in the cases indicated in the law. They are the conditions that are considered necessary to protect public order, public security, public health, morals, or the rights and freedoms of others (23).

Fourth - the sanctity of housing and the right to privacy:

Article 10 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states: "There are inviolable homes that may not be entered except in the cases specified in the law and in the manner stipulated therein."

Article (81) of the Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure No. 9 of 1961, amended in 2006, stipulates: "It is not permissible to enter and search homes unless the person who wants to enter and search his home is suspected of being a criminal offender, a partner or an accomplice in it. Or the holder of things related to the

crime, or the concealment of a person accused of him. " In the articles that follow, the legislator clarifies the procedures for entering and inspecting homes.

Article (88) of the Jordanian Code of Criminal Procedure No (9) of 1961, amended in 2006, stipulates that: "The public prosecutor may seize all letters, letters, newspapers and publications at post offices, and telegraph offices have all telegraphic messages, and telephone conversations may be monitored whenever This was useful in showing the truth. "

Article (12) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, and Article (17) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966 stipulated the right to privacy. This right is considered one of the most important rights that a person should enjoy, because the person's enjoyment of this right guarantees the preservation of his secrets and his private life, and keeps them away from the knowledge and interference of public authorities or others in them.

The French jurist Carbonet defined the right to privacy as: "the secret domain in which the individual has the power to exclude any interference from others, or it is the person's right to be left quiet" (24).

Fifth - the right to private property:

Article eleven of the Jordanian constitution of 1952 states that: "No one's property shall be expropriated except for the public benefit and in return for just compensation, as specified in the law."

Article 12 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 also stipulated that: "No compulsory loans shall be imposed, nor movable or immovable property confiscated except in accordance with the law."

Sixth - The Right to Work:

The first paragraph of Article 6 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states that: "3- The state guarantees work and education within the limits of its capabilities, and guarantees tranquility and equal opportunities for all Jordanians."

Article 23 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states that:

1- Work is a right for all citizens, and the state must provide it for Jordanians by directing and promoting the national economy.

2 - The state protects work and creates legislation for it based on the following principles:

A- Giving the worker a wage commensurate with the quantity and quality of his work.

B- Determining the weekly working hours and granting workers weekly and annual rest days with pay.

C- A special compensation report for dependent workers, and in conditions of layoffs, sickness, disability and emergencies arising from work.

D- Defining the conditions for the work of women and minors.

E- The worker is subject to health rules.

F- Free trade union organization within the limits of the law.

Work in Jordan is regulated by the Jordanian Labor Law No. 8 of 1996 and its amendments. Article 23 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 stipulates the right to work. Article (24) deals with the right to rest and leave, and Article 6 and Seven of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966 stipulates the right to work. Article 8 of the aforementioned Covenant on the right to form trade unions, and in the introduction to the constitution of the International Labor Organization, stipulates that the right to work is one of the basic rights on which the principle of human rights and freedoms is based, and the realization of this right is not only necessary for a person's livelihood, but also for the development of his personality.

Seventh - Freedom to Practice Religious Rites:

Article 14 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states: "The state protects the freedom to perform the rituals of religions and beliefs in accordance with the customs observed in the Kingdom, unless they are contrary to public order or against morals."

This freedom was stipulated in Article (18) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, and Article (18) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966.

Eighth - Freedom of opinion, expression, press, and other intellectual freedoms:

Article fifteen of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952, amended on 1/10/2011, states the following:

1 - The state guarantees freedom of opinion, and every Jordanian has the right to freely express his opinion in speech, writing, photography and all other means of expression, provided that it does not go beyond the limits of the law.

2- The state guarantees freedom of scientific research and literary, artistic, cultural and sports creativity in a manner that does not contradict the provisions of law, public order or morals.

3- The state guarantees freedom of the press, printing, publishing and the media within the limits of the law.

4- It is not permissible to suspend newspapers and media outlets nor revoke their licenses except by a court order in accordance with the provisions of the law.

5- In the event of the declaration of martial law or emergency, the law may impose on newspapers, pamphlets, books, mass media and communication limited censorship in matters related to public safety and the symptoms of national defense.

6- The law shall regulate the method of monitoring newspaper resources.

The Encyclopedia of Politics has defined freedom of opinion as: The freedom of the citizen to express his opinion in all public matters without being subjected to any punishment. Freedom of expression takes many different forms and frameworks, from freedom of speech to freedom of writing to literary and artistic freedom, and thus includes: freedom of the press and the media and freedom of speech "(25).

Ninth - The Right to Education:

The first paragraph of Article 6 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states that: "3- The state guarantees work and education within the limits of its capabilities, and guarantees tranquility and equal opportunities for all Jordanians."

Article 19 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states that: "Groups have the right to establish and establish their schools to educate their members, provided that they observe the general provisions stipulated in the law and are subject to government oversight in their programs and directives."

Tenth - The right to peaceful assembly and formation of associations, unions and political parties:

Article 16 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952, amended in 2011, states that:

1- Jordanians have the right to assemble within the limits of the law.

2- Jordanians have the right to form associations, trade unions, and political parties, provided that their goals are legitimate, their means are peaceful, and that they have regulations that do not violate the provisions of the constitution.

3- The law shall regulate the method of forming societies, unions and parties, and monitoring their resources.

Public meetings in Jordan are regulated by the Public Gatherings Law No. 7 of 2004 and its amendments, the Associations Law No. 51 of 2008 and its amendments regulate associations, and political parties in Jordan are regulated by the Political Parties Law No. 39 of 2015.

Article (20) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, and Article (21) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966 stipulated the right to assemble, as well as the right to form associations Article (20) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, and Article (22) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966.

Eleventh - the right to address public authorities:

Article seventeen of the Jordanian constitution of 1952 states: "Jordanians have the right to address public authorities on personal matters on their behalf or in matters related to public affairs in the manner and conditions specified by law."

Twelfth: the right to hold public office:

Article Twenty-Two of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states that: "1- Every Jordanian has the right to hold public office according to the conditions specified in the law or regulations / 2- Appointment for permanent and temporary public positions in the state and public administrations according to the conditions specified in the law or regulations."

This right was stipulated in the second paragraph of Article 21 of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The Jordanian Civil Service System No. 82 of 2013 and its amendments in Article (40) thereof stipulated the conduct of competitive examinations and personal interviews to fill vacant positions (26), which is considered the basic method for assuming public office.

We note from the foregoing that the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments have stipulated the rights and freedoms that every human should enjoy so that his dignity is safeguarded and his humanity fulfilled. The constitution has been keen to achieve direct protection of rights and freedoms, as it cites explicit constitutional texts, clearly categorically, in which it clarifies the rights and freedoms enjoyed by citizens that are consistent with the rights and freedoms contained in international covenants, chiefly the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, and the Special International Covenant With economic, social and cultural rights, and since the constitution is the supreme law in the legal state, all the authorities in the state must respect these constitutional texts and not violate the rights and freedoms contained in them, because by doing so they violate the constitution, which makes them lose their legitimacy, and they must be held accountable.

The constitutional principles guaranteeing rights and freedoms in the Jordanian constitution and its amendments

Despite the serious constitutional protection provided by the aforementioned texts for public rights and freedoms and despite the importance of direct constitutional protection for it, the prosperity of these rights and freedoms, and their realization for the desired goal of the stipulation, which is to preserve the freedom, dignity and humanity of the human being, and unleash his energies to be a dear and generous actor in his society, needs

a suitable environment that guarantees the maintenance of these rights and freedoms. . The Jordanian constitutional legislator was keen to create this environment, and formulated this environment through a number of constitutional principles upon which the legal state is based, such as the principle of separation of powers, the principle of supremacy of the constitution, the principle of the rule of law, the principle of the independence of the judiciary, and other principles and guarantees mentioned in the texts The Jordanian constitution, which achieves indirect constitutional protection of public rights and freedoms, and researchers will try to clarify these principles and their role in protecting rights and freedoms, ensuring that citizens enjoy them, and not violating them or diminishing them from any of the state authorities:

First - the principle of the nation's sovereignty:

Article 24 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states the following: 1 - The nation is the source of powers, 2 - The nation exercises its powers in the manner indicated in this constitution.

According to the principle of the nation's sovereignty, the nation is the sovereign, and it includes all individuals who belong to the state in the past, present and future to no end (27).

Second - the principle of separation of powers:

The Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments did not explicitly stipulate the introduction of the principle of separation of powers. However, this is clearly demonstrated through the organic separation and the functional separation of powers that are clarified by the constitution's provisions. Article 25 of the Jordanian constitution stipulates the following: "The legislative authority is vested in a council. The nation and the king is composed of the upper and lower houses. "Article 26 of the aforementioned constitution also stipulated the following: "The executive authority is entrusted with the king and is exercised by his ministers in accordance with the provisions of this constitution." As for Article 27, amended in 2011, it stipulated: "The authority the judiciary is independent, and it is exercised by the courts of all degrees, and all judgments are issued in accordance with the law in the name of the king." The articles of the constitution specified the jurisdiction of each authority separately.

The main purpose of the principle of separation of powers is to preserve freedom and prevent tyranny (28) resulting from the concentration of power in the hands of a single body or person. Therefore, it was necessary to distribute the powers among several bodies so that each agency could monitor the other body and stop it at its borders (29), and prevent it from being arbitrary if it exceeded or abused the authority (30).

Consequently, if the legislative authority assaults the rights and freedoms of citizens set forth in the constitution, through the laws it enacts, the executive authority can dissolve Parliament. Likewise, if the executive authority, during the exercise of its powers, assaulted the rights and freedoms of citizens, or violated them or detracted from them, the legislative authority can, through the means it possesses, force it to stand at its limits and hold it accountable for its behavior, so it can ask questions to it to inform public opinion of its deviation. It can also direct interrogations to the minister responsible for violating the rights and freedoms of citizens, and also raise the ministerial responsibility of the responsible minister or the government as a whole and drop it if the House of Representatives decide to withdraw confidence from it by the absolute majority of the total number of its members. Ministerial responsibility is the weapon that the legislative authority possesses in exchange for the right to dissolve (31), and the consequence of the withdrawal of confidence is that the government must resign in the case of joint ministerial responsibility, and that the minister must resign his post in the case of individual ministerial responsibility in accordance with Article 54 of the amended 1952 Jordanian constitution in 2011.

Thus, the consequence of the flexible separation of powers is that both the legislative and executive authority will be keen to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens stipulated in the constitution and not to violate, diminish or confiscate them, for fear that the other authority will hold them accountable, and that every authority will seek to empower citizens from using these rights and freedoms and creating the appropriate conditions for that.

Third - the principle of the rule of law:

The Jordanian constitution did not explicitly stipulate the principle of the rule of law, and this principle is one of the principles upon which the legal state is based, and it is one of the principles recognized, whether or not they are explicitly stipulated in the constitutions. In its broad concept, this principle means: "the rule of law in the state, so that its provisions and rules override every will, whether the will of the ruler or the ruled" (32). What is meant by law as its broadest sense that is all the rules of positive law existing in the state, on top that is the constitution? This principle means that: "The legal rule comes above the will of all individuals, rulers or ruled, and obliges them all to follow its rulings ... If they do not adhere - especially the rulers - to the legal rule; their unlawful behavior will turn into an unlawful and unlawful act" (33).

This principle aims to make the ruling authorities in the state subject to rules that are binding on them, as they are binding on individuals. The state is not a legal state except when all the governing bodies in it are subject to rules that bind them and are superior to them (34).

The Supreme Court of Justice in Jordan was the one that heard the case for annulment, but after the constitutional amendments that took place in 2011, Article 100 of the amended 1952 Jordanian constitution

stipulated that: "All types of courts, their degrees, divisions, and their jurisdictions, and how they are administered, shall be determined by a special law provided that this law provides for the establishment of an administrative judiciary in two phases. The second paragraph of Article (128) of the amended Jordanian constitution in 2011 also stipulated: "All laws, regulations and other legislative acts in force in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan upon the entry into force of this constitution shall remain in force until they are canceled or amended by legislation issued in accordance with it within a period of time maximum of three years. " Based on these two articles, the Jordanian Administrative Judiciary Law No. 27 of 2014 (35) was issued, and it was clarified in Article Three of it that the Administrative Court in the Kingdom consists of the Administrative Court (which is the Court of the First Instance) and the Supreme Administrative Court (which is the Court of the Second Instance) and was specified in Article Five The jurisdiction of the Administrative Court, as it has jurisdiction over all appeals related to final administrative decisions, and defined the types of final administrative decisions that the court has jurisdiction to consider the cancellation lawsuit directed against it and requests for compensation according to the case for cancellation. Article 7 of the aforementioned law defines the reasons for the cancellation lawsuit, which are lack of jurisdiction, violation of the constitution, laws or regulations, error in their application or interpretation, and the association of the decision or its issuance procedures with defective form, abuse of authority, and the defect of the reason.

Fourth - the principle of the supremacy of the constitution:

The Jordanian constitution of 1952 did not explicitly stipulate the principle of the supremacy of the constitution. However, this principle is one of the principles upon which the legal state is based, and this principle is one of the recognized principles whether explicitly stipulated in the constitutions or not, and it means that the constitution as the supreme law in the state does not On top of it is another law (36), and the supremacy of the constitution includes two aspects:

The first: objective sublimity, and the second: formal sublimity.

Monitoring the constitutionality of laws is an important guarantee that must be in place to protect rights and freedoms, because the constitutional texts that define the rights and freedoms of individuals cannot preserve their highness that they enjoy, and they cannot be binding on all authorities in the state if the legislative authority is able to It enacts laws that violate it, or it has restricted these rights and freedoms while regulating its practice. This was prohibited by the Jordanian constitutional legislator in an explicit constitutional text, through what was stated in the first paragraph of Article 128 of the Jordanian constitution amended in 2011, which states: "Laws issued under this constitution to regulate rights and freedoms shall not affect the essence of these rights and freedoms. " Therefore, it was necessary to have an oversight over the constitutionality of laws in order to verify the extent to which laws and regulations respect the constitutional rules that represent the top of the pyramid in relation to the legal rules in the state. Therefore, it was rightly said that: "Constitutional oversight is an affirmation of the principle of the supremacy of the constitution and its supremacy over the rest of the legislation in the state, a real and strong guarantee to protect and safeguard the freedoms of individuals, and to safeguard the rights of individuals and ensure their respect" (37).

And overseeing the constitutionality of laws may be political prior to the issuance of the law, such as the oversight carried out by the French Constitutional Council, and it may be judicial, and it is of interest to us in the subject of our research, as judicial oversight of the constitutionality of laws is intended to entrust the task of verifying and verifying the extent of conformity of laws to the constitution with the judicial authority. This oversight may be censorship of abstinence or censorship of abolition. The oversight of the constitutionality of laws in Jordan was prior to the amendment of the Jordanian constitution on 10/1/2011 (38).

However, when the 2011 constitutional amendment was issued, Article 58 of the amended 1952 Jordanian constitution stipulated that: "A constitutional court shall be established by law, which shall be located in the capital and considered an independent and independent judicial body, and shall be composed of at least nine members, including the president, appointed by the king." Article fifty-nine of the constitution also specified the court's jurisdiction to oversee the constitutionality of laws and regulations in force, and the interpretation of the constitution. Constitutional Court Law No. 15 of 2012 was issued which stipulated that the Constitutional Court is an independent body with legal personality, and specified that it exercises its competence to abolish the law or the system in violation. To the constitution through either a direct claim or a subsidiary plea of unconstitutionality (39), as the first paragraph of Article (60) of the amended 1952 Jordanian Constitution specifies the parties that have the right to "appeal directly to the Constitutional Court about the constitutionality of laws and regulations in force.

Thus, the importance of the principle of the supremacy of the constitution, and the consequent oversight of the constitutionality of laws, as a guarantee for protecting the rights and freedoms stipulated in the constitution. It is represented that if any law or system is issued that detracts from these rights and freedoms, or limits or confiscates them, in a manner contrary to what is stated in the constitution, then this law or system will be unconstitutional. The Constitutional Court can cancel it based on a direct lawsuit filed by one of the bodies specified by the constitution exclusively, or on the basis of a subsidiary defense submitted by one of the parties

to the case pending before a court that applies to the dispute the law whose constitutionality is challenged, and the judiciary must refrain from applying it based on failure Its constitutionality.

Fifth - the principle of the independence of the judiciary and guaranteeing the right to litigation:

Article 27 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952, amended in 2011, states: “The judicial authority is independent and is exercised by the courts of all degrees, and all judgments shall be issued in accordance with the law in the name of the king.”

Article 97 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 states that: “Judges are independent, and there is no authority over them in their rulings except for the law.”

The second paragraph of Article 98 of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952, amended in 2011, clarified that a Judicial Council undertakes all matters related to regular judges.

Judicial independence leads to affirmation of the rule of law and protection of citizens' rights and freedoms (40). “Judicial independence is not complete except under a democratic system, who believes in the rule of law, and in which the rights and freedoms of citizens are respected, and there is no legislative preclusion in it between the individual and from suing the public authority in any act that is harmful. It is not taken from the ordinary judiciary in order to be tried before special or exceptional courts, except that all these matters, even if possible, are considered part of the definition of the rule of law. However, they are not considered part of a formal definition of the independence of the judiciary unless the judiciary is considered as an authority ... A state without a truly independent judiciary will be a society deprived of the rules of law, which are the controls that protect public freedom from usurpation, aggression and slurs”(41).

The principle of the independence of the judiciary guarantees the existence of an independent and impartial authority that individuals can resort to in order to defend their constitutional rights and freedoms if they are subjected to any assault or derogation, without fear of the influence of the executive or legislative authority or any person regardless of their influence or power over the judiciary while looking into the cases brought before it. With regard to the provisions issued by.

In order for the individual to be reassured that his rights and freedoms are safeguarded, the constitutional legislator has stipulated a number of guarantees that the individual enjoys before the courts, including the openness of the trial, and that the principle is innocent, which is expressed as: “The accused is innocent until proven guilty by a final judgment. It also stipulated that no civilian may be tried in a criminal case before a court whose judges are not all civilians except for the crimes of treason, espionage, terrorism, drug crimes and currency counterfeiting (Article 101) amended in 1958.

Conclusion:

In the conclusion of our discussion of the topic: “Protection of rights, freedoms and constitutional principles for them in the Jordanian constitution and its amendments”, it is worth clarifying some of the results that I have reached through this research:

Results:

1- The Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and its amendments - especially the important constitutional amendments that were made in 2011 - stipulated a number of rights and freedoms enjoyed by Jordanian citizens, including equality before the law, personal freedom, freedom of movement and residence, the right to property, and others, which were consistent with The Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966, where these rights and freedoms in their entirety constitute an integrated structure that protects the humanity of mankind, preserves his dignity and strengthens his belonging to his homeland.

2- The clear constitutional texts that define the rights and freedoms enjoyed by Jordanian citizens provide direct constitutional protection for those rights and freedoms, as all public authorities in the state must respect these rights and freedoms, and not violate them or diminish them, because they thus respect the constitution that defines their jurisdiction From which it derives its legitimacy, if it encroaches on the rights and freedoms of citizens protected by the provisions of the constitution, then by doing so, it has violated the constitution itself, which makes it lose its legitimacy, and leads to the nullity of its behavior and calls for its accountability and accountability.

3- The constitutional legislator is keen to provide an appropriate environment to protect the rights and freedoms guaranteed by the constitution, by adopting a number of constitutional principles that collectively provide indirect constitutional protection for those rights and freedoms, even though these principles are not directly related to constitutionally protected rights and freedoms.

4- The constitutional principles adopted by the Jordanian constitution of 1952 and its amendments provide serious guarantees for the protection of rights and freedoms, as we note that the principle of separation of powers leads to the existence of mutual control between the executive and legislative authorities in a way that prevents any of them from violating the rights and freedoms of citizens for fear of provoking their responsibility and holding them accountable By other authority.

Recommendations:

1- We call on the Jordanian constitutional legislator to explicitly stipulate in the constitution that it is impermissible to amend the constitutional texts related to rights and freedoms, unless the purpose of this amendment is to increase the citizens' enjoyment of those rights and freedoms, because the rigidity of these texts leads to the achievement of more effective protection of these rights and freedoms, the legislative authority cannot amend them for any reason unless the purpose of the amendment is to increase the citizens' enjoyment of them.

2- We call on the Jordanian constitutional legislator to explicitly stipulate in the constitution to accept the direct claim that laws and regulations are unconstitutional if this claim is submitted by unions, parties and associations and not limited to the Senate, Parliament and Council of Ministers only, because unions, parties and associations represent a wide range of citizens, and from its right to demand the abolition of laws and regulations that are inconsistent with the constitution and that may include diminishing the rights and freedoms of the citizens who belong to it.

3- We call on the Jordanian constitutional legislator to explicitly stipulate in the constitution the creation of a kind of prior constitutional oversight of laws and regulations related to the regulation of constitutionally protected rights and freedoms, to ensure the extent of their constitutionality, in order to prevent the issuance of laws or regulations that contradict the essence of constitutionally protected rights and freedoms or violate their foundations.

4- Exempting lawsuits and defenses that citizens bring in defense of their constitutionally protected rights and freedoms from judicial fees, so that citizens can defend them without fear of any obstacles or financial difficulties.

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